

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEANS OF RADIOELECTRONIC COMBAT WITH A SWARM OF UAVS**Volodymyr Kniaziev***PhD, Senior Research Scientist**Research and Design Institute «Molniya»**of National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»,**47, Shevchenko Str., Kharkiv, 61013, Ukraine***Abstract**

Analysis of modern military conflicts clearly demonstrates the high efficiency of using unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). Countering UAVs has become very important for reducing combat losses of equipment and personnel. A significant part of existing means of combating implements the mechanical impact of UAVs using gun-missile systems. Electronic warfare systems, as a rule, implement the following functions: detection, identification of communication channels, generation of electromagnetic fields with similar parameters, but at a higher level. However, these systems are ineffective when using a swarm of UAVs. The article considers the efficiency of alternative radio frequency directed energy weapons (RFDE). The results of the assessment show that the use of RFDE to combat a swarm of UAVs does not solve this problem, since it has limited efficiency.

Keywords: unmanned aerial vehicles, combating, electronic warfare system, directed energy weapon, swarm, power, electromagnetic field level

The rapid development of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV), including those operating under the control of artificial intelligence, determines new conditions for conducting combat operations. The use of UAVs capable of delivering explosives over considerable distances poses a danger to rear facilities of military and civilian infrastructure. Therefore, effective combat against UAVs has become very important. A significant part of the existing means of combat implements mechanical damage to UAVs using gun and missile systems. However, this method is very costly, as shells and missiles cost much more than kamikaze UAVs. In addition, the limited supply of shells does not allow for effective destruction in the event of a large number (swarm) of UAVs being used in the future.

Developers of electronic warfare (EW) systems are seeking to increase the destabilizing capabilities of these systems. Currently, most of the existing EW systems disrupt communication with the operator and positioning systems. When a UAV is detected, control codes are read, an electromagnetic field (EMF) is created with a level above the working one, and in some cases, control is intercepted. The R&S®ARDRONIS should be mentioned as a fairly effective system that operates on this principle. Conversely, UAV developers are seeking to reduce the possibilities of information influence, for example, by replacing the air control channel with optical fiber, quantum communication, installing an artificial intelligence unit, storing flight tasks in autonomous mode, etc. It can be assumed that in the near future the effectiveness of EW systems with information jamming will sharply decrease.

Therefore, within the framework of this article, the main attention is paid to determining the real effectiveness of the use of Radio Frequency Directed Energy Weapon (RFDEW) systems [1], which are capable of causing physical force damage to the element base of UAVs. Such systems do not require precise knowledge of the technical

characteristics of UAVs, as these systems are usually ultra-wideband.

The failure of one of the following systems leads to the disruption of UAV operation:

navigation device; sensor system; executive system; automated control system.

The automated control system, consisting mainly of microelectronic elements, is most vulnerable to the influence of powerful electromagnetic radiation. When it fails or provides distorted information, the unmanned aerial vehicle loses its orientation and control, thereby being unable to perform its task. It should be noted that in general this topic has many aspects that are considered in a large number of scientific and technical publications, for example [2 - 4]. Physical impact is carried out by high-power microwave (HPM) devices that are able to disrupt the operation of electronics by a radiated electromagnetic pulse (EMP). The voltage and current surges that EMP creates in electronic circuits can destroy electronic circuits within reach. Since modern UAVs are based on electronics, HPM is potentially an effective solution.

It is clear that the requirements for the required level of EMF intensity with certain time parameters, capable of destroying electronic components, are directly related to the level of immunity of such components, combined by an electrical circuit. Typically, data on the immunity level of specific components is provided without taking into account the actual electrical circuit. In this case, the level of resistance may be significantly overestimated. The ratio of the immunity level to the level of radiated EMF determines the potential range of the RFDEW system.

Let us determine the parameters of the modulated harmonic electromagnetic fields that form the most powerful EW systems listed in Table 1 (columns 1 - 4). The initial data on the technical parameters of existing EW systems were obtained from the Internet. We consider data on these systems, because the corresponding data on

RFDEW systems is still unavailable. However, the physics of electromagnetic field radiation is similar for both types of system.

To assess the distance at which the destabilizing effect of the electronic warfare system can cause irreversible damage, it is assumed that the electric field strength should be above 200 V/m. This is the level at

which the immunity of the equipment to the action of the electromagnetic field in the gigahertz range is tested according to the MIL STD 464C standard [5]. The results of calculations using formula (1) from the IEC 61000-4-3 standard [6] are shown in Table 1 (column 5).

Table 1

Data on the parameters of electronic warfare systems

Name EW System	Antenna type	Radiation power, kW	Maximum range, km	Effective impression distance, m
1	2	3	4	5
Borisoglebsk -2	logperiodic	100	30	60
Divnomorye	parabolic	300	300	100
Krasnukha	parabolic	300	300	100
Rtut	logperiodic	300	1,0	100
Shipovnik-AERO	dipole & logperiodic	200	10	85
Complex AN/SLQ-32(V)6 SEWIP Blk 2	phased array type AN/SLQ-32	1000	-	500

$$E = k P^{0.5} / d \quad (1)$$

where:

E is the field strength (RMS value) (V/m);

k is the antenna constant with a value characteristic of free-space propagation in the far field;

P is the power (ERP) (W);

d is the distance from the antenna (m).

Nearby reflecting and absorbing objects alter the field strength.

The value of k was estimated using formula (1), based on the assumption that the E-field intensity at the maximum distance exceeds the maximum "working" field intensity of the communication channel 1 V/m by at least 20 dB (~20 times). The approximate value of the coefficient for the systems listed in Table 1 is $k \sim (40 - 100)$.

The energy potential of mobile complexes is determined by the power of the engines of the base vehicles. For ground-based complexes, this is the power of the engine of the EW/REP base vehicle. Wheeled and tracked vehicles act as such bases. The power consumption of a mobile base platform for EW purposes is up to 80% of the base engine power. Thus, for the most common types of base platforms, the engine powers is as follows: APC - 80 – 150 kW; KamAZ - 130 kW; KrAZ - 140 kW; MAZ - 225 kW, which is consistent with the data in Table 1.

According to [1], a significant advantage of RFDEW systems is the low cost of one shot. However, the initial cost of some types of DE can be significant. For example, DoD officials said that the cost to fire a DE weapon is approximately the cost of fuel needed to generate the system's power for firing and cooling, or about \$1-\$10 per engagement. By comparison, defensive missiles can cost millions of dollars per shot.

The fundamental question is: what amplitude-time parameters of pulses and their repetition rate are most effective? Reducing the duration of pulses allows for an increase the repetition rate and increase the peak value

of the field strength. The following options are considered:

- single pulse with HEMP parameters (1.2 / 23 ns);
- a sequence of ultrashort pulses of the form (0.1 ns / 2 ns) with a specified repetition rate;
- other options, if the equipment allows.

The author tested the level of resistance of electronic equipment to single HEMP pulses. A household electronic calculator BrilliantBS-132 was selected to implement the resistance level assessment procedure. The choice is based on the following circumstances. The quality of the calculator's functioning during the tests is easily checked without additional diagnostic equipment. The product has an autonomous power supply, so the influence of the power cable tracing is excluded. During the test, the calculator was sequentially located in three orthogonal orientations relative to the electric field strength vector. The installation of elements, including the power supply, was performed in the plane of the calculator's electronic board. Given the relatively small thickness of the product, compared to the other two overall dimensions, the greatest influence of the magnetic field was expected in the case when the panel is perpendicular to the direction of the magnetic field vector, with simultaneous vertical (along the E-field vector) arrangement of the larger size of the calculator. The test results showed that at an electric field strength of 17.7 kV/m, the effect of zeroing the information on the calculator screen is manifested, but its operability is preserved. At an electric field strength of 35.2 kV/m, the calculator malfunctioned (the screen went blank without the ability to restore functionality by a "turn off-on" operation). Analysis showed that the failure was caused by controller degradation.

According to the study [7], the immunity levels of the Keytex kt-uhf-h-02 reader works at the ETSI (EU) frequency 865.6 - 867.6 MHz, searches, writes and reads labels of EPC global Gen2 (ISO 18000-6C) standards were investigated under the condition of exposure to ultrashort pulses (USP) EMI with the following parameters:

- amplitude of the influencing field pulses up to 30 kV/m;
- front duration / duration of the emitted pulses within 0.2 / 0.5 ns;
- the frequency of pulse repetition 1 kHz;

Under the action of an USP with electric field strength of 30 kV/m and a frequency of 1 kHz, the system worked in normal mode and met the stability requirements.

Thus, it should be assumed that for the destructive effect on UAVs by High-Power Microwave pulses, it is necessary to ensure an electric field intensity of at least (25 - 35) kV/m. I believe that these values can be reduced by increasing the pulse repetition rate to ensure a sufficient level of absorbed energy. Let's consider what practical results have been achieved so far.

Publication [8 - 10] provides information on the current status of RFDEW systems, such as: Tactical High Power Microwave Operational Responder (THOR), Phased High Power Microwave System, Airbase High Power Microwave System Extended Range (CHIMERA). In [9], there is a reference to the possibility of effective operation of High-Power Microwave systems at a distance of up to 2 km, with a radiated power of 500 kW, with an antenna diameter of 2 m, a beam width of 1 degree, for a wavelength of 30 cm. Based on such data, decisions are made on the financing of research.

Based on the presented data, we will make a forecast of the possible level of electric field intensity at a distance of 2 km. The calculation was made using formula (1), in which the following values were adopted: $P = 5 \cdot 10^5$ W; $d = 2 \cdot 10^3$ m; $k \sim 4 \cdot 10^4$ (the value was obtained based on the fact that 1 degree is $3 \cdot 10^4$ steradians). The expected value of E reaches 14 kV/m (at a distance of 1 km, respectively 28 kV/m). The area that such a beam will cover in space at a distance of 1 km is approximately 300 m². The question remains what kind of pulses will be emitted, with what frequency of sending. The obtained values E are not very encouraging for high efficiency at the indicated distances.

China has announced [11] a significant breakthrough in its secretive high-power microwave weapon program, claiming the system survived firing thousands of intense pulses in a recent test. Named the Hurricane-3000, the microwave weapon is reportedly capable of generating electromagnetic pulses of up to 80,000 V/m. This immense power would disrupt or destroy electronic components in enemy weapon systems, including large swarms of drones. During the test, the Hurricane-3000 allegedly fired more than 5,000 full-power pulses and endured the blasts without any sign of malfunction. It is clear that these reports do not contain technical data that would allow us to assess the actual effectiveness. However, earlier in the advertising materials the impression distance was indicated as $\sim (100 - 300)$ m, which is trustworthy because it correlates well with the results shown in Tables 1.

Conclusions

1. To combat the swarm of UAVs, RFDEW systems are being developed. However, the effectiveness of such systems depends on the quality of the development of UAV samples.

2. Electromagnetic waves in the frequency range > 300 MHz are attenuated by more than 60 dB by conductive materials. Thus, the internal space of the UAV will be reliably protected. Protection of antenna-feeder paths is effectively carried out by installing appropriate protective elements that are compact for ultra-high frequencies.

3. According to the media, we can consider the effectiveness of the systems at a distance of 100 m to 300 m to be proven, but without data on the design of the UAV.

4. In the author's opinion, the creation of a counter-UAV may be more effective. It is clear that counter-UAVs can also form a swarm.

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